

2024 Ada Lovelace Workshop on Modelling Mantle and Lithosphere Dynamics

1-6 September 2024, Sète, France

Poster Session - September 2-3

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 Arnould Maëlis²
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 Desiderio Matteo¹
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 Van Driel Jack
 Yamato Philippe
 Zhou Xin²
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- ¹ 1-min presentation scheduled on Monday 2nd September 10:15-10:45
- ² 1-min presentation scheduled on Tuesday 3rd September 10:00-10:45

Poster Session - September 4-5

Aellig Pascal³
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Kaus Boris
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 Le Pourhiet Laetitia
 Li Zhong-Hai/ Wang Yang
 Lin Jia Xun³
 Liu Sibiao³
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 Maierová Petra
 Mcmillan Mitchell³
 Neuharth Derek³
 Olive Jean-Arthur
 Plimmer Abigail³
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 Puckett Elbridge Gerry
 Pusok Adina

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 Wang Yang³
 Wang Yijun³
 Weiler Tatjana³
 Werner Niklas³
 Whipp David
 Xu Chong³
 Zhang YINUO³

- ³ 1-min presentation scheduled on Thursday 4th September 10:00-10:45

Towards a New Geodynamic and Geochemical Reconciliation of the Origin of the DUPAL Geochemical Anomaly in the South Atlantic and Southwest Indian Oceans

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Keywords — mantle convection, petrology & geochemistry, plumes

The question of the origin, structure, and composition of the mantle source of the DUPAL geochemical anomaly (Dupré & Allègre 1983), a southern hemisphere anomaly with high radiogenic Pb and Sr isotopic ratios, continues to generate active debate within the geophysics and geochemistry communities. A range of geochemical hypotheses have been proposed that involve contrasting interpretations or inferences of the geometry, vigor, and temporal evolution of the mantle-convective origin of the DUPAL anomaly. To address this challenge, we employed time-dependent thermal convection models that reconstruct the 3-D evolution of global mantle structure. These reconstructions employ a back-and-forth nudging (BFN) method for time-reversed thermal convection initialized with a present-day tomography model derived by jointly inverting seismic-geodynamic-mineral physical data (Glišović & Forte 2016). Although the African Large Low Shear Velocity Province (LLSVP) is often believed to contribute to the geochemical distinctiveness of these anomalies, our study provides geophysical and geochemical arguments that challenge this common assumption. Reconstructed particle trajectories in the mantle reveal two distinct and far-removed paleo-subduction-zone source regions for the South Atlantic and Southwest Indian Ocean hotspots. In addition, we find that these hotspot-related particle trajectories avoid the high-density core of the African LLSVP, providing compelling evidence that their distinct isotopic signatures reflect an inheritance of deep-sourced subducted material. In summary, this multidisciplinary investigation provides novel insights on paleo-subduction sources for hotspot geochemistry in the South Atlantic and Southwest Indian Oceans.

References

- [1] B. Dupré et al. [Pb–Sr isotope variation in Indian Ocean basalts and mixing phenomena](#). *Nature* 303, 142–146 (1983).
- [2] P. Glišović et al. [A new back-and-forth iterative method for time-reversed convection modeling: Implications for the Cenozoic evolution of 3-D structure and dynamics of the mantle](#). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 121, 4067–4084 (2016).

1. Introduction

The origin, structure, and composition of the mantle source of the DUPAL geochemical anomaly, characterized by high radiogenic Pb and Sr isotopic ratios, remains debated. We employed time-dependent thermal convection models to reconstruct the 3-D evolution of global mantle structure. The reconstructions employ a back-and-forth iterative (BFI) method for time-reversed thermal convection initialized with a present-day tomography model derived by jointly inverting seismic-geodynamic-mineral physical data (Glisovic & Forte 2016)

Time-reversed conservation of thermal energy equation:

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \beta \Delta^2 \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right) = \rho c_p \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{k} \nabla T - \alpha T \frac{d\rho}{dt} - \Phi - Q$$

Figure 1 (Glisovic & Forte 2016)

2. Geochemistry

We observe that the ratios of 206Pb/208Pb, 207Pb/208Pb, and 87Sr/143Nd distinguish the South Atlantic DUPAL hotspots (Tristan, Gough, Discovery, and Kerguelen) and the Southwest Indian Ocean/East African (SIOA) hotspots (Reunion, Comoros, Mayotte, Kilimanjaro, and Tanzania). The ratios observed in the Southwest Indian Hotspot group, indicate sediments derived from continental crust while the South Atlantic Hotspots show a pelagic sediment signature.

3. Tomography-Based Modeling of Particle Trajectories in Earth's Mantle

We employ an accurate Lagrangian numerical procedure for explicit tracking of individual particle paths in time-dependent mantle flows that was successfully tested under the North Atlantic (Glisovic & Forte 2019).

To evaluate the degree of mixing associated with each mantle plume, we set up a configuration of twelve equally spaced particles within a two-degree radius, centered around a single particle at the present-day hotspot location. These particles were subsequently simulated to trace their paths backward in time. The degree of mixing was quantified by modelling the spatio-temporal divergence of this cylindrical array of particle tracks

Figure 3. Particle tracks of Tristan and Mayotte showing distinctly different source regions as well as geochemical mixing

4. "Spokes" and "Edges"

Traditional analyses of ocean islands' relationship to LLSVP involve correlating surface hotspots to projected "edges" of LLSVPs, assuming perfectly vertical connections across 2700 km depth. By employing explicit particle tracking inside our reconstructed mantle flow, we are freed from the need to rely on such simplistic and highly idealized spoke-like plume constructions and their relationship to an assumed compositional "edge" of an LLSVP. The variable definitions of these "edges", based on differing tomography models, can significantly bias their interpretations. Furthermore, a high degree of spatial resolution in the selected tomography model(s) is implied by these vertical hotspot connections.

5. Plate Tectonic Reconstructions

To address questions around the sources of chemical heterogeneity, our analysis includes the entire extent of the hotspot particle trajectories, rather than just focusing on those purely ascending segments that intersect with the seismic D" layer. The figure below shows a compilation of plate reconstructions and the reconstructed particle track locations at 250 Ma. There are two widely separated families of hotspot-related particle trajectories (see figure 3) and they strongly correlate with plate tectonic reconstructions of ancient subduction zones in the Neotethys and Southern Panthalassa margins of the Pangean supercontinent, which provide distinct chemical signatures of recycled sediments.

Figure 6 Particle positions of Tristan, Gough, and Discovery as well as Reunion, Comoros, Mayotte, Kilimanjaro with plate reconstructions from GPlates software

6. Shona, Bouvet, and Mantle mixing

The Shona and Bouvet hotspots are also associated with distinctly different mixing dynamics. This is made evident (see figure below) by substantially larger spatio-temporal divergence of the cylindrical particle arrays surrounding each of these two hotspots. This divergence reveals that much larger volumes of the mantle are sampled by the upwelling that connects the deep mantle to these surface hotspots. We, therefore, propose that the observed difference in geochemistry between Shona and Bouvet hotspots and the other South Atlantic hotspots is more likely related to its mixing dynamics within the upwellings and not to the proximity to the putative "edge" of the African LLSVP.

Particle track of Shona showing dramatically different mixing dynamics

7. Conclusion

Our multi-disciplinary approach integrating independent geophysical modeling, geochemical analysis, and plate reconstructions, strongly suggests that the deep mantle heterogeneity expressed in surface basalts in the South Atlantic and SIOA hotspots can be attributed to two geographically distinct, widely separated source regions of past subduction. This clear differentiation in source regions, coupled with the observed movements of the hotspot particle trajectories away from the high-density core of the African LLSVP, brings into question the traditional arguments regarding the relevance of hotspot locations relative to ad hoc definitions of LLSVP "edges." This novel interpretation provides a fresh insight concerning the origin of the geochemical signatures expressed by these hotspots. This clarified perspective is supported by our ability to explicitly track the history of movement of material across the mantle.